

“Synthesis of Zeolites from Coal Fly Ash”

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Introduction:

What are Zeolites?

Zeolites are hydrated allumin osilicate minerals from inter linked tetrahedral of alumina(AlO_4) And silica(SiO_4).in simple words,they are solids with a relatively open three dimensional crystal structure built from the elements like aluminum,oxygen,& silicon with alakali or alkaline earth metals (Sodium,Pottassium & magnesium) plus water molecules trapped in the gaps between them.

Types of Zeolites

Zeolites are mined in many parts of the world; most of the Zeolites are commercial & are produced synthetically. The applications of Zeolites are more as compared to natural Zeolites. There are nearly 50 different types of Zeolites (Clinoptilolite, Chabazite, Phillipsite, mordenite,etc) with varying physical & chemical properties, crystal Structure and chemical composition,particle density, cation selectivity, pore size, & strength.

Zeolites are of two types

1. Natural Zeolites

- According to the US Geological Survey,there are about 40 naturally occurring zeolites, forming in both volcanic & Sedimentary rocks..Most common Zeolite minerals are Analcime, Chabazite, Clinoptilite, Mordenite, Natrolite, Phillipsite & Stilbite.
- Natural Zeolites are non porous for example, Natrolite, $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{XSiO}_2 \cdot \text{yH}_2\text{O}$.

2. Synthetic Zeolites

- Synthetic (Artificial) Zeolites (around150) have been designed for specific purposes,the best known Zeolites are, Zeolite A ,Zeolite X&Y etc.These are Porous.
- They are prepared by heating together china clay, & soda ash.

Difference between Natural & Synthetic Zeolites:

Synthetics are manufactured from energy consuming chemicals whereas naturals are processed from natural ore bodies. Synthetic Zeolites have silica to alumina ratio 1:1 & Clinoptolite (Clino) zeolites have a 5:1 ratio.

Basic Structure of Zeolites:

- Zeolites are three dimensional micro porous, crystalline solids with well defined structures that contain aluminium, silicon & Oxygen, in there regular frame work cations & water are located in the pores.
- Water moves freely in & out of these pores but the Zeolite frame work remain rigid.

Description of the Chemical Structure of Zeolite

- Primarily, Zeolites are built from $(\text{SiO}_4)^{4-}$ & $(\text{AlO}_4)^{5-}$ which are tetrahedral & infinitely extended in a three dimensional network,they are linked togethre by a shared atoms of oxygen.

Schematic of the Building Unit of Zeolite Structure.

- The pore size & shape present in a Zeolite framework affect the adsorption properties of a Zeolite & its ability to act as molecular sieve. Zeolites classification can be done base on the pore size present in the zeolite frame work & this can be done defined by the number of T atoms present in the framework. Where T=Silicon or Aluminium ion.

Importance and Applications:

The cage like structure of Zeolites makes them useful in all sorts of ways. One of the biggest

everyday uses for zeolites is in water softness & water filters in ion exchange water softness. For example Hard water (rich in calcium & magnesium ions) is piped through a column filled with sodium containing zeolites. The Zeolites trap the calcium & magnesium ions & realease sodium ions in their place.so the water becomes softer but richer in sodium.every day laundry & dish water detergents contain Zeolites to remove calcium & magnesium and soften the water so they work more effectively.

Chart showing the percentage utilization of synthetic zeolites

Use of Zeolite has advanced in the following areas:

a) In Agriculture:

- Zeolites are have been used successfully as soil additives to improve the yield of agricultural products. The mercury adsorption by plants & its subsequent entry into the food chain can be restricted using natural Zeolites.the ammonia enriched zeolite acts like a fertilizer to give high efficiency in agricultural.
- The Zeolites also be used in the culitivation of common vegetables & flowers.these are used in the food industry.

b) In Animal Production:

- Clinoptilolite (natural Zeolite)have shown Significant gain in weight & high resistance to sickness than those fed with normal diets.zeolites have been shown to affects the characterisitics of eggs.The clinoptilolite helps to imporove the weight of the albumen & yolk in egg.
- Mineral adsorbents such as natural Zeolite & bentonite can be added to chick diets to prevent food poisoning resulting from the presence of mycotoxins in their diet.

c) Cosmetic & Dermatological Application:

- Zeolites in powdery form have found applications in the treatment of athletic foot & it has proven to be effective it also shorten the time required for the healing of bruises & wounds from Surgery.

d) Bone Formation:

- Zeolite A containg Silicon has resulted in an increase in the thickness of egg shells in hen, these Zeolites also have significant effects on the formation & structure of bones.

e) Enzymes Encapsulation:

- This technique also given exciting pharmalogical application of Zeolites & meso porous Silicate encapsulation of different ions & molecules.
- The Zeolite surface has been applied for the treatment of skin diseases & as support materials for enzymes & antibodies.

Materials and Synthesis methods :

Materials :

- There are some of the basic materials which are in the Zeolites are
- Silicon dioxide, Aluminium Oxide, Faujasite, Sodalite, Analcime, Nickel, Caesium, Palladium, Zirconium, Vanadium, Gallium, Nobel Metal, Cobalt, Strontium, Ruthenium, Pozzolan.

Zeolite

Synthetic methods of Zeolites:

There are three methods used in the synthesis of Zeolites & they include

1) Hydrothermal Method:

Hydrothermal method is the earliest method of the synthesis of Zeolites. The reactants are usually put inside a Teflon lined autoclave with hydrothermal synthesis pressure for optimum Zeolite production. This method is much easier & cheaper than other methods.

Auto-clave kit

2) Solvothermal Method:

This method of Zeolite Synthesis involves the use of a Solvent to produce the Zeolite. Since the hydrothermal method can also be said to be a member under this classification, since water is most common solvent. Other solvents such as alcohols, hydrocarbons, pyridine, etc.

This is another special category of Solvothermal synthesis method in which the solvent used are mainly ionic compounds.

Zeolite Synthesis from Coal Fly Ash:

Coal Fly Ash :

Fly ash is produced in massive amount as a waste material of burning fossil fuels (Coal combustion) for the thermal generation of Electricity.

3) Ionothermal Method:

Thermal Power Point

Raw Cosh Fly Ash

- This residue being utilized for various purposes including in Cement & concrete Production. There are different types of fly ash including class F & class C generated by burning black coal & Brown Coal respectively.
- Basically Zeolites are the natural minerals which are derived from raw coal fly ash that contains the Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , $Ca_3Al_2O_6$, etc...

Brief procedure:

- Collect that powder in the beaker, further we made Acid treatment for raw coal fly ash to remove Sulphur content.
- Raw Coal fly ash was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid (HCl) & kept it for 1 hour for

the deposition of the particles at bottom of the beaker. Finally the fly ash was neutralized by washing with deionized water & allowed for drying.

- After the acid treatment (washing & drying) weigh the treated fly ash.
- Also we make the basic treatment for acid treated fly ash. Allow this mixture for a prolonged heating process of about 72 hours with giving 100 degree Celsius temperature.
- After that we take the sample in plastic or glass holder. Make the treated Coal fly ash sample for XRD analysis, after that compare both graphs (Raw Coal fly ash to treated Coal fly ash).

Schematic representation of Zeolite Synthesis:

Characterization Techniques : XRD, SEM, TGA, DTA,

- Synthesised products Zeolite were determined by using X-ray diffraction spectroscopy with diffraction angle 2θ ranging from 0-80 degree using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at 40 Kv & 40 milliampere.
- Surface morphology of Fly ash & Synthetic Zeolite was analyzed by SEM.
- In SEM analysis Samples were coated with thin layer of Gold make them Conductive.
- The Synthetic Zeolite was further characterized by Thermo gravimetric Analysis(TGA), Differential Thermal Analysis(DTA), with the heating rate of 10degree centi grade per minute from ambient temperature to 800⁰ C in argon atmosphere.

X-Ray diffraction patterns for (A) untreated fly ash, (B) fly ash treated at 100⁰ C in 3.0M NaOH at 1 atm pressure for 3 days

Thermal analysis curves (TG & DTA) of the synthesized NaA Zeolite is shown in the below :

Thermal analysis (TG, DTA) curves of synthesized NaA Zeolite.

- Endothermic peak exists in the DTA & weight losing slope in the TGA curve demonstrates the maximum rate of H₂O losing is temperature around 200 degree.
- According to the literature , NaA Zeolite presents a Cubic structure:
- According to the TGA curve, the maximum weight loss, which is corresponded to water content of the sample, is about 12 %.
- The DTA curve of the as Synthesized zeolite shows several thermal effects.

- Moreover, SEM photos indicated the uniform. SEM images of Fly ash, Synthesized Zeolite by Solid transformation method & EDS analysis.
- The Spherical particles with relatively smooth Surface & irregular round shaped predominated for the raw Fly ash.

Result and Conclusion:

- The X-Ray diffraction after crystallization shows the crystalline phase of Quartz and mullet gradually distinguished comparing with JCPDS file.
- The reduction in peak intensities 700 degree celcius may be the result of the transformation of Na-A Zeolite to the pH & SOD Zeolite

which have lower CEC & adsorption performance of ZFA decreased.

- The adsorption of ZFA increased with rise of crystalline time & declined rapidly.
- Zeolite tends to transform into SOD & pH Zeolite upon prolonged reaction time.
- A high charge Zeolitic material can be produced from fly ash by heating the fly ash in strong base.
- Formation of NaA Zeolite was ascertained by mean of defferent characterization technique including XRD, SEM, TGA/DTA.
- The Fly ash Zeolites were relatively unstable compared to other aluminosilicates partly because of the high specific surface.

- The NaOH treated fly ash used in laundry detergents, also it has many commercial /non commercial applications.

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